

Opportunities and Advancement in Pugal Embroidery of Western Rajasthan

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Abstract:

Pugal Embroidery unfolds a narrative steeped in culture, history, and artistic ingenuity, emerging as a cherished traditional craft originating from the captivating desert city of Bikaner in the northwest Indian state of Rajasthan. This magnificent form of embroidery, a testament to the dedication of artisans preserving its heritage, has traversed generations, embodying a tale of skill and innovation. Celebrated for its intricate and vibrant designs, Pugal Embroidery graces various fabrics, predominantly clothing and accessories. The meticulous process commences with the careful selection of high-quality materials, such as wool, silk, or cotton, onto which skilled needle workers meticulously hand-embroider with precision. Drawing inspiration from regional flora, fauna, and traditional themes, these designs form a visual symphony mirroring Bikaner's arid terrain. Executing this craft demands time, skill, and an innate sense of color and composition. The fabric comes to life through the interplay of textures and reflective features created by threads, beads, sequins, and mirrors. Pugal needlework, often depicting images from Rajasthani history and mythology, plays a pivotal role in preserving indigenous tradition. Recently, it has garnered attention not only for its aesthetic allure but also for its economic significance, as artisans explore new domestic and international markets to sustain their livelihoods. This study meticulously traces the evolution of Pugal embroidery's traditional craft, motifs, and materials, delving into the history, conservation, and economic importance of this art form. Recent advancements have ushered in a new era for Bikaner's Pugal embroidery, with artisans incorporating contemporary technologies to enhance their traditional craftsmanship. Collaborations with modern fashion designers and companies have propelled this ancient art form into the global spotlight, enriching fashion and lifestyle items with a sense of exclusivity and luxury through the exquisite and distinctive designs of Pugal embroidery.

Keywords: *Contemporary Adaptations, Needlework, Pugal Embroidery, Product Diversification Traditional Craft, Sustainable Practices*

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1. Introduction

The land of royalty, Rajasthan is the largest state of India. This little piece of heaven on earth is rich in culture. It has something for everyone, be it exquisite monuments, remarkable palaces and forts, lively folk dances, alluring handicrafts, mouth-watering food which attracts not only Indians but also tourists from around the globe. Besides the forts, palaces and deserts. The state is a treasure trove of handicrafts and textiles such as blue pottery, marble works, lac bangles, leather wear, inlay work on brass and wood, terracotta sculptures, tie and dye, block printing, embroidery, carpets and durries. Grounded to their roots, people of Rajasthan are very welcoming and reflect their colourful heritage with pride.

With the motive to record the craft of Pugal embroidery, this study compresses the journey of exploring the handwork of artisans. Located at Pugal, Bikaner district, houses incredibly talented and skilled artisans executing rich embroidery (Kashidakari). The Pugal embroidery is exercised by simple people, who pour their hearts out in doing the intricate embroideries with so much passion, and resilience that has helped in keeping it alive. The beauty of such precision shines bright in the products of kashidakari. Passed on, by generations before them, the embroidery now progresses towards the future with added help from various non-profit organizations reaching out to the artisans, offering them work and raw materials, further introducing the craft to a newer market, and widening

the customer base. It's fascinating to note that the village's embroidery work has garnered attention from notable brands like IKEA, Fab India, Rangсутra etc.

1.1 Literature Review

Embroidery is an expression of self, rendered with patience and dedicated hard work. It is an art rightly described as “image by needle”. The term “Kashidakari” literally means ‘needle work’. Kashidakari is an age-old practice of producing exquisite clothing items by using a needle and thread. The embroiders of this beautiful craft migrated to western Rajasthan, Gujarat and adjoining areas at the time of India- Pakistan separation in 1971. Meghwals are an ethnic tribe in northwest India and Pakistan, considered descendants of Saints who brought rain. They belong to the Schedule Caste social class and are known for their vibrant jewelry and clothing. They coexist with other desert tribes like Rabari and Bhil in remote communities in the Thar Desert, sharing vocabulary, sensibility, and visual cultural identification. Both embroideries are exquisite and unique. The pugali embroidery started as a traditional way of reusing fabrics. To give the old and ragged clothing a new look, the poor community started doing embroidery on them. Separating yarns from waste pieces of fabrics, spinning them together and using for embroidery. This is how Kashida was born. Initially, it was done for dowry purpose only but soon after migrating, the Meghwal community realised its prominence and converted it into a source of income.

Pugal block in Rajasthan is a significant cluster of embroidery craft, with approx. 2000 artisans engaged in ethnic work. The finest work comes from Bikaner and Barmer Districts, and features floral patterns, human and animal figures, and abstract designs. Embroidery items include women's wear, kurtas, cushion covers, dress material, bed covers, and bags. Pugal region in Bikaner, Rajasthan, is known for its traditional Meghwal embroidery work, primarily done by girls and women. The villages of 8AD, 9AD, and 2AD offer unique experiences and unique names due to their proximity to the India-Pakistan border [1].

Figure 1: Geographical Indication of Embroidery

Pugali embroidery, primarily produced in the Pugal region of Bikaner, Barmer district of Rajasthan, and Kutch region of Gujarat, features vibrant color schemes and intricate geometric patterns. This needlework, known as Kashidakari, includes Pakke ka kaam, Mukke ka kaam, and various forms, with each region showcasing unique techniques and raw materials. The Pugal region of Bikaner specializes in Kashida, using kharak, Sindhi, and Kambiri stitches and embellishments. The Barmer district of Rajasthan uses mukke ka kaam, featuring metallic threads couched with embroidery thread. Gujarat's Kutch area focuses on Pakke ka kaam, using embroidered threads twice to strengthen and make Kashidakari more durable. These regions use different techniques to create visually appealing and intricate designs.

Kashidakari, a popular needlework in Kashmir Valley, is believed to have been introduced by Persian Sufi saints. Its intricate patterns and style are reminiscent of Persian influences. Unlike Pugal needlework in Rajasthan, Kashidakari in Kashmir and Pugal needlework in Rajasthan share similarities in name and effort, but are distinct and unique [2].

2. Methodology

This research is grounded in fieldwork, secondary data, and conversations with Pugal craftsmen.

2.1 Raw Materials

Pugal embroidery is majorly done on cotton linen, Kota doria, khadi (cotton & Wool), silk and Mangalgiri fabric. Interlining (Astar), a fabric used for lining is also used in some of the products. There is a 60:40 ratio, where 60% of the embroidery is done on stitched clothes and 40% is done on unstitched fabric. An embroidery threads (rangoli

and anchor), gold & silver threads for mukka work, and embellishments like Sitaar, miniya, kungri and kaanch are utilised to beautify the embroidery. Singhare and supari are covered with fancy threads a used for decorating various products. Phunde (Tassels) are also used to decorate the edges of the products. Now a days, Kaanch ka kaam(Mirror work) is seen on the fabric with a very minimalistic embroidery to meet customer requirements and be aesthetically pleasing. Needle, scissors, blades, thread cutters are used for cutting & finishing. The original artisans are so skilled that they do not use an embroidery ring or frame whereas the learners and new artisans do use them.

2.2 Process

There are the following processes steps required for pugali embroidery such as mentioned below

- **Pattern Cutting:** The fabric is cut into the size of the resultant product. If the embroidery is being done for brands, the trusts provide them with the already cut and checked pattern piece.
- **Tracing:** Traditionally, no tracing or sketching of design on cloth is done. Women used to draw whatever they felt like. Original Meghwal descendants still follow this rule whereas the new artisans prefer tracing the design first. The design is printed on a sheet of paper and holes are punched through. A mixture or paste of ash and chunna powder is dabbed onto the fabric.
- **Embroidery:** After the tracing, embroidery starts. For Sindhi embroidery, square motifs are first created and then other parts. For kharak, the borderlines are created first, then further it is divided into four boxes. First, the borders are completed using chain stitch and then alternate boxes are filled. At last, finishing is done, cutting the loose threads and redoing if something comes out wrong or undone.
- **Stitching:** The stitching can be done either before or after embroidery. Very few of the artisans do know how to stitch, so that part is taken care by the organisations.
- **Finishing:** The quality of the final products is checked through different parameters like smooth, uniform and neat stitch, accuracy of motif placement, cleaned under layer of the fabric and uncut threads, no errors and omissions in the motif with advised colour. Additionally, careful monitoring can prevent missing elements and ensure even and well-defined borders, resulting in high-quality hand-embroidered products that meet the desired standards and showcase the artistry and beauty of this traditional craft.

3. Types of Embroidery Practice in Pugal

The harshness of the desert of Rajasthan is balanced by the brilliant colors used in the Kashidakari like Soof, Pakka, Kharak, Kambiri, and Sindhi. They are typically used to make a wedding bridal goods.

Figure 2: Soof Embroidery

3.1 Soof

Fine, delicate stitching with geometrical motifs is known as soof. Soof is of two types: Kachcha soof are borderless, parallel, equal filling stitches that run vertically, horizontally, and diagonally. Pakka soof is the same as kachcha soof; the only difference is that it is with boundaries.

Figure 3: Kharak Embroidery

3.2 Kharak

The geometric needlework technique known as kharak was developed by counting the structural elements of the cloth and, as the name suggests, is reminiscent of the tactile qualities of the date tree. In this style, the artisan works out the structure of geometric patterns with an outline of black squares, then fills in the spaces with bands of satin stitching that are worked along the warp and weft from the front.

Figure 4: Mukke Ka Kaam

3.3 Mukke ka kaam

Mukke ka kaam is a type of embroidery technique used in the kharak kashida which includes the extensive use of gold and silver zari or metallic thread. The couching is done through buttonhole stitch, so that the aesthetic appearance of the metal threads does not get disappeared.

Figure 5: Sindhi Embroidery

3.4 Sindhi

The interlacing stitch used in Sindhi embroidery is executed over a laid-out foundation of threads. Sindhi embroidery is commonly used on garments, home decor items, and accessories, reflecting the rich cultural heritage of the Sindhi people.

Figure 6: Kambiri Embroidery

3.5 Kambiri

An ascending or descending pattern can be seen in kambiri kashida, mostly geometrical motifs are embroidered. Nowadays, it is not practiced much. It is a durable embroidery as pakke ka kaam is done where a tight square of chain and double buttonhole stitch is supplemented with the satin stitch that are used to create dense pattern on the cloth. Mostly fly and satin stitches are used in this embroidery. The color palette mostly comprises of shades of red, dark green, gold or yellow with a relatively black or white background.

4. Designs & Motifs of Pugal Embroidery

Pugal, Barmer and Kutch regions, they carried various motifs and designs with themselves which then became a very vital part of the embroidery. The dominance of geometric patterns in all three types of kashida along with the substantial usage of floral designs, various motifs that can be seen in the embroidery are Hunnuji, Kaanch or teek, Peendi, Moriyo and Chokdi etc. Apart from these, there is no particular story or inspiration behind these motifs and

the artisans present their skills with the help of their creative mind and embroider the designs which they know or generally see around themselves. The use of mirrors in the Pugal embroidery helps to ward off the evil eye and is considered as a symbol of protection.

To make the product as attractive as possible, the artisans use a range of designs and brilliant colors. On the items the craftsmen create for their own use, you can see the use of vibrant embellishments, along with plenty of beading, sitara, and other sequins with elaborate and specially designed patterns. However, as the years went by and each new generation had less and less time to devote to it, the degree of intricacy and complexity decreased. Modern designs are based on the preferences of the younger generation, and minimalism and soft hues are crucial. The filling inside the designs has names like Tardo, koth, kando, Bakhiyo, Pakko, and Ghodo. They draw inspiration for their motifs from the environment around them such as flora, fauna, houses etc.

Table 1: List of Motifs of Pugal Embroidery

Name of Motif	Pictorial	Name of Motif	Pictorial
Chokdi		Floral	
Moriya		Sindhi Pancholi	
Hunnuji		Geometric Motifs	
Kaanch (Mirror)		Penndi	

5. Types of Stiches in Pugal Embroidery

The different categories of pugal embroidery employ number of distinct techniques which differentiates them from one another, and the intricate geometric patterns include a variety of stiches which are used in the production of embroidery. Utilizes fine and delicate thread work, often employing intricate stiches like satin stitch, cross stitch, running stitch for a gracious appearance [3].

Table 2: List of Stiches in Pugal Embroidery

Type of Stitch	Type of Stitch
<i>Feather Stitch (Dantiya)</i> Feather stitch is a stitch resembling overlapping feathers.	<i>Pakka Kanera</i> A zig-zag stitch, with loops at the corners.
<i>Tipiya</i> French Knot stitch.	<i>Keelne</i> A double sided blanket stitch.
<i>Cretan Stitch</i> Cretan stitch is an embroidery stitch consisting of a series of diagonal stiches arranged in a zigzag pattern, resembling the peaks and valleys of the Cretan landscape.	<i>Pankhiya (fly stitch)</i> It is a V shaped stitch which can be done singularly or detached in rows.
<i>Cross Stitch (Bachda)</i>	<i>Buttonhole Stitch</i>

Cross stitch is a basic embroidery stitch that forms X-shaped stitches and is commonly used for creating intricate designs and patterns.	Buttonhole stitch is a looped embroidery stitch used to secure the edges of fabric or create a buttonhole-like border.
<i>Chain Stitch (Lath)</i> Chain stitch is a looped embroidery stitch formed by linking individual stitches, creating a chain-like appearance.	<i>Soof(satin)</i> It is a filling stitch which gives a sense of satin like appearance, and it is one of the most used stitches in Kashida.
<i>Back Stitch (Bakhiya)</i> A Backstitch is a stitch that creates a solid line by stitching backward and then forward. The reverse of this stitch is stem stitch.	<i>Zarda (zardozi)</i> Use of metallic threads and embellishments in the embroidery
<i>Running Stitch (Moriyo)</i> Running stitch is a basic hand-sewing stitch that creates a straight line of small, even stitches used for various sewing and embroidery purposes.	<i>Koot (knot stitch)</i> This stitch is used to place small, filled circles at equal intervals to increase the aesthetic appeal.
<i>Choon</i> Small decorative triangles.	<i>Cording</i> Kaccha tanka done over chaandi.
<i>Pakka Soof</i> It is the same as kachcha soof; the only difference is that it is with boundaries.	<i>Kacha Soof</i> These are borderless, parallel, equal filling stitches that run vertically, horizontally, and diagonally.
<i>Single Dantiya (Blanket Stitch)</i> This stitch is used to give an edge to something, maybe a mirror or border to the embroidery.	<i>Double Dantiya</i> Double sided fly stitch.
<i>Aadhi Chain</i> Variation of chain stitch, in which each chain has a gap between each other.	<i>Purri Chain</i> It is a type of stitch which forms small loops one by one and is used to enhance the motif.
<i>Chain kaccha taaka</i> A combination of chain stitch and running stitch.	<i>Lace Kashida</i> It is a twirl like stitch, which has a thick dense structure.
<i>Herringbone Stitch (Kanado)</i> Herringbone stitch is a decorative embroidery stitch that forms a series of slanted parallel lines resembling the bones of a herring fish.	<i>Chune wala Dantiya</i> It is chain stitch which is used to give a proper finishing border to animal motifs.
<i>Kaccha Tanka</i> Raw stitch/running stitch	<i>Kaccha Kanera</i> Herringbone stitch.

6. Color of Pugal Embroidery

Pugal embroidery is bright and playful. The colours used are vibrant and contrasting. It's colour palette mostly consists of red, blue, green, yellow and orange. The base fabric colour is usually in contrast with the colour of the embroidery threads. It's amusing that the use of all bright colours is not hard on the eye and creates harmony. The artisans skilfully blend a wide range of hues, including red, orange, green, blue, and yellow, to adorn fabrics with eye-catching and joyful embroidery. The result is a visually stunning and culturally rich textile art form that celebrates the essence of Indian craftsmanship.

7. Product Ranges of Pugal Embroidery

As there is a custom in Pugal region that marriages, this craft was initially performed to fulfil dowry requirements and as souvenir when she leaves her home to join another family. Later, this craft began to benefit them financially, and the artists were able to support themselves and make a living.

The product selection for embroidered goods is extensive and varied, including a wide range of things from different industries. Embroidery gives a sense of elegance and individuality to clothing and accessories, including intricately embroidered garments like blouses, kurtas, etc., and elegant home textiles like embroidered bed linens, curtains, and ornamental cushions. On handbags, backpacks, and clutches, delicate stitching is on display. Keychains and patches are examples of personal accessories that have exquisitely stitched patterns. In the worlds of fashion, home design, and branding, embroidery is a highly sought-after ornament due to its adaptability. The

Meghwal artisans who live in the Pugal villages of 8AD, 7AD and 2AD create things for both the commercial market as well as for their personal needs.

- *Rumal*: During the marriage ceremony, the bride holds the self-embroidered rumal and it is a mandatory ritual. It takes 2-3 months to complete.
- *Indrani/Hinduni*: A sturdy circular base, which is placed on the top of head, over which earthen pots are placed. It helps in creating a balance while walking with a pot on head, over long distances. Brides are expected to bring their own hinduni when they arrive at their in-law's house.
- *Surma Dani*: A beautiful container used by women of the house to keep their traditional Surma bottle.
- *Choti Khali*: Cover to decorate supari.
- *Cushion Cover*: A long cushion cover is made according to the length of the bed.
- *Khalichi*: A small embroidered Purse.
- *Bigna/Pankhi*: A traditional hand fan having a metallic frame covered with cloth attached to a handle. The fan is used in a swinging motion.
- *Kanghi*: A pocket size comb is decorated with pearls and beads.
- *Gochna*: Newly married woman used to carry chapattis in a heavily embroidered piece of fabric to the farm to show respect towards their husbands.
- *Thaal Posh*: Used to cover pooja ki thaal

8. Recent Product diversification in Pugal Embroidery

There is no certain change in the type of stitches used in this embroidery, but the designs have evolved over time. Around in 4 decades, the designs were spread all over the products and one can see excessively elaborate designs, but nowadays a minimalistic approach is applied to meet the current market demands. There is no change in the motifs as well, just the confined version of same old motifs can be seen in cushion cover, bedsheet, kurta, sarees, shrugs, kaftans, tops, bag etc.

However, the people of Pugal generally make products for selling purpose only but there are some products which are still embroidered for dowry purpose.

Figure 7: Modern Products by Pugal Embroidery

9. Market of Pugal Embroidery

The complexity of the design determines the production cost. Although this needlework is hard to get in Bikaner's local market places, other companies like Ikea and Jaypore do demand it. Hand embroidered products specialized and luxurious appeal define the market environment. Consumers that value artisanal craftsmanship, originality, and personalized touches in their purchases are catered to by hand embroider goods. But the availability of hand embroidered goods is constrained due to problems with scalability and mass production, keeping their exclusivity. The complexity of the design and the quantity of items that the artisans produce determine the daily wages that are paid to them.

A Self-Help Organization famous for its solar looms is located in the Napasar town under Bikaner. The Napasar Hathkargha Vikas Samiti (NHC) is known for weaving and embroidery. Shanti Maitri Mission Sansthan (SMMS), a voluntary NGO, presently working in Pugal tehsil and adjoining areas of Bikaner district since 1996. To increase sales, SMMS has been organizing an annual event called "HUNAR BAZAAR" to support indigenous artists and entrepreneurs. It is an effort to introduce the crafts done in Bikaner to local people. Overall, SMMS has been like a torch in the dark for artisans by providing them with regular work, raw material supplies and business strategies [4]. Some of the established brands like Fab India, IKEA, Swadesh C&N etc generate the demand for pugal embroider products and communicate through NGOs or the people involved in communicating to artisans.

10. Present Scenarios of Pugal Embroidery

In the present, this embroidery craft is facing challenges such as limited market demand, a lack of awareness, financial struggles, and difficulty in preservation due to dwindling interest and inadequate training opportunities. Access to resources is also a concern, along with competition from mass-produced goods, which leads to cultural erosion. Being located near a border presents numerous challenges, including the necessity for individuals to obtain government permissions. This lengthy process discourages people from visiting the area, leading to a decline in their interest.

However, there are opportunities for growth and recognition, including leveraging online platforms, collaborating with designers, tapping into ethical and sustainable trends, participating in craft tourism, organizing workshops and exhibitions, incorporating the craft in education, and receiving local support. By embracing these opportunities and addressing the challenges, the craft can gain visibility, preserve its heritage, and secure a place in the creative landscape.

11. Future Scope of Pugal Embroidery

In the future, this embroidery crafts have the potential to experience a remarkable revival and gain widespread recognition. As people increasingly seek genuine and handcrafted products, the cultural significance and craftsmanship of these traditional techniques will be appreciated. Looking at the future through the lens of creative ideas, the embroidery has stood the test of time, breathing its way through what every age had its changes to offer. Keeping the roots and the heritage intact, the Pugal embroidery has flourished by expanding its threads to stitch the designs of a new era. Talking about the embroidery itself, the motifs, colours and most importantly the execution has maintained its rhythm throughout the years in traditional embroidery. Major options such as generation reluctance or adaptation, providing sufficient education & awareness, minimalistic approach, experimentation with raw material, collaboration with Brands/Designers and end uses shift from home textile to apparels.

Efforts to preserve cultural heritage will lead to increased awareness and support for these crafts in specific regions and communities. Digital platforms will connect artisans with a global audience, fostering knowledge exchange and sustainable livelihoods. Social media platforms will serve as showcases for artisans and enthusiasts, attracting a broader audience to appreciate and celebrate these crafts. Specialized exhibitions and cultural events will provide exposure and opportunities for artisans to connect with enthusiasts and investors.

Table 2: SWOT analysis of Pugal Embroidery

SWOT	Description
Strength	The original embellishments that artisans create are exceptionally unique and distinctively their own. Compared to other craftsmen, these artisans are skilled to execute embroidery on every material. Their years old experience has helped them in gaining interpersonal skills and complete the work in short time frame
Weakness	Artisans are not able to connect directly to the market and face several transportation difficulties. Lack of awareness about the craft among the localities and hence not recognised widely. Insufficient knowledge among artisans on how to benefit from Government schemes.
Opportunity	Well execution and accuracy of the geometric patterns can be their distinctive feature as motifs are crafted with perfect symmetry. The craft could be combined with different crafts like block printing, tie and dye and others. The artisans are inclined towards creative exploration of the craft. Receive assistance & funding from the government's Ministry of Textiles and NGO's. Connecting artisans to global customers to e-commerce is a lifeline for many.
Threats	Ongoing trends of minimalistic designs can lead to the extinction of traditional embroidery designs. Lack of awareness among young generations. Lack of a GI tag prevents them from receiving many government benefits and recognition.

Due to limited recognition, companies and designers have little to no engagement with them, which prevents their growth. Health of artisans is affected.

12. Conclusion

Pugal embroidery is a delicate textile technique that is rich in color, texture, and patterns, much like any other ancient craft. Even though most people, including those who reside in the surrounding areas of this craft cluster, are unaware of this craft, the embroidery is so distinctive in terms of its complex geometric patterns that it merits recognition as a well-known craft and should be valued more due to the artisans' meticulous skills. It is ideal to acquire momentum in the present market and can compete with the ongoing trends because of the brilliant colors and the neatness of the handmade work. Discovered a lot of fascinating information while conducting research for this field, including the fact that artists are eager to raise awareness of their handicrafts and possess a willingness to develop their own identities via their exceptional skill set. The interplay of tradition and proficient embroidery in their lives, a narrative of perseverance despite change. Their commitment persisted in the face of obstacles like sustainability and market access because they were encouraged by organisations that integrated tradition with modernization.

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